

The deformation and failure response of UHMW-PE composite to localised blast loading

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Ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene composite

- Chemical composition

- Gel-spinning

Orientation low
Crystallinity <60%

Orientation >95%
Crystallinity up to 85%

- Fibres are arranged in unidirectional ply with ~20% matrix, stacked in $[0/90]_n$ and hot pressed to produce laminates

Background

- UHMW-PE fibre reinforced composites are extensively used to provide protection against ballistic threats
- Due to their high strength and toughness, can potentially be a good material for blast protection
- There is very limited studies on the blast performance of UHMW-PE composite
- This work looks at the deformation response and rupture performance of UHMW-PE composite due to localised blast loading

Target material

- Target material (Dyneema® HB26)
 - Polyurethane matrix
 - 83% fibre volume fraction, fibres ~17 µm in diameter
 - 10 mm thick, $[0/90]_{80}$ layup
 - Hot pressed at 128°C and 20 MPa
- Targets are 400x400 mm with 14 mm diameter bolt holes drilled out
- The strike face was spray painted black to limit light transmission from the blast
- The rear face was spray painted with a speckle pattern for DIC

Experimental setup

- Rupture threshold
 - 50 mm diameter cylindrical PE4 explosive charge at fixed SOD of 50 mm
 - Charge mass varied to determine limit to rupture target
 - Blast impulse determined by measuring displacement of pendulum

- Dynamic deformation
 - 50 mm diameter cylindrical PE4 explosive charge at fixed SOD of 50 mm
 - Charge mass varied up to rupture threshold
 - DIC using 2 high speed cameras

Blast pendulum at BISRU UCT (courtesy of McDonald et al. 2018)

High speed camera within blast pendulum (Curry & Langdon 2017)

Rupture threshold

- The rupture threshold of a 10 mm Dyneema® HB26 target is between 25-30 grams of PE4 at 50 mm SOD
- Below the rupture threshold
 - Significant permanent bulge deformation
 - Reversed snap buckling (RSB) occurred forming a depression in the centre of the panel
 - Composite melting on the strike face, and delamination strip on the back face
- Above the rupture threshold
 - Same response as panel subjected to blast loads just below the rupture threshold
 - Small perforated region

Target from 25 gram PE4 charge (left) strike face, (middle) rear face and (right) perspective view

Target from 30 gram PE4 charge (left) strike face, (middle) rear face and (right) perspective view

Deformation

- DIC was performed with charges below the rupture threshold.
- At 10 grams, the centre point deformation rises rapidly and then stays constant.
- For 15 and 20 gram charge, the centre point increases rapidly and then inverts due to elastic recovery, leading to reversed snap buckling (RSB).
- Results show the larger the explosive charge, the greater the elastic recovery leading to larger depression in the centre.
- RSB has been observed in GRFP [3] and aluminium [4] and has been shown to be dependent on the timing and magnitude of the blast load and structural properties of the target.

Failure mode

- The fibre failure modes from perforated targets was investigated using scanning electron microscopy
- Fibres showed tensile stretching, necking and fibrillation
- No difference were observed between fibres on the strike, mid plane or back face of the target

Fibre on the strike face

Fibre on the mid-plane

Fibres on the back face

Conclusion & Future work

- Localised blast testing was performed on UHMW-PE composite
 - The rupture threshold was determined for a 10 mm thick target and the failed fibres showed failure in tension via straining and fibrillation
 - The deformation response was measured and showed that close to the rupture threshold, the panel would load and invert, leading to a central depression
- The results form the basis for future numerical simulation and validation.

Reference

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